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Mapping Nicosia's
urban centre
1960-2020

An Overview on the demography
of the urban centre of Nicosia:
Challenges, methodology and remarks

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An Overview on the demography of the urban centre of Nicosia: Challenges, methodology and remarks

Antigone Heraclidou

CYENS Centre of Excellence/ Cyprus University of Technology and

Esra Plümer Bardak

Association for Historical Dialogue and Research

INTRODUCTION

Demography consists of the characteristics of a place's population. It reflects changes of many variables such as gender, ethnicity, race, age, religion, literacy rate, births, deaths, marriages. Changes in the demography of a place happen due to several factors, like the economic situation, natural disasters, wars, foreign policy, governmental decisions, etc.

This paper attempts an overview of the demographic evolution of Nicosia, the capital of Cyprus, from 1960, when Cyprus became an independent state after an 82-year long British colonial rule, until 2020, when the Covid-19 pandemic broke out. Cyprus makes a unique case, compared to, at least, other European countries, because since 1974, the Republic of Cyprus (RoC) exercises effective control over only two-thirds of the island's territory. The 1974 war undoubtedly consolidated the separation of the two communities that had started in the 1950s-60s with population movements and enclaves and therefore changed the demographic makeup of the urban centre of the island. Other developments that took place afterwards also affected the city's demography demonstrating that the demographic composition of a city is tightly linked to its political history.

This overview is a part of larger research project called Deep Mapping Nicosia's urban centre, 1960-2020 where we examine the transformation of the urban centre of Nicosia on three levels, namely, demography, business activity and monument building, in conjunction with key socio-political events occurred during this period. The project does not attempt to analyse in detail the Census results conducted during this period on both sides of the divide. What follows is a description of our methodology and the challenges we encountered during our research on the demographic composition of the island and a summary of our key observations and remarks.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Cyprus was under foreign rule for centuries before becoming an independent country. As part of the Ottoman Empire for more than 300 years, from 1571 until 1878, a significant Muslim community was living in the island, enjoying a privileged treatment compared to the Christian Orthodox majority. This disproportionate balance of power, rights and privileges existed between the two communities changed with the introduction of British rule in 1878 and the restructuring of the justice system. However, the existence of two separate communities, each with a distinct ethnic identity, religion, language, and national orientation in what was supposed to be a British Colony continued and grew stronger to the extent that impeded the development of a common Cypriot identity, under the newly established independent Republic of Cyprus in 1960. Besides, the end to the British rule came after an armed revolt carried out by EOKA¹ during which intercommunal rivalry culminated with each community becoming more clinched on their national goals, i.e. *enosis* (union with Greece) for Greek Cypriots and *taksim* (division of the island into two parts) for Turkish Cypriots. This is not the time or the space to discuss the origins or the development of these national aspirations, but their inculcation within the Cyprus society was so strong that it persisted even after the end of the British rule. In fact, as Joseph argues, the removal of the Colonial Administration left the way open for the two motherlands to develop close relations with the newborn state and seek promotion of their national goals on the island.²

The establishment of the Republic of Cyprus, 1960

On August 16, 1960, Cyprus became an independent state, after 82 years of British colonial rule. The island's independence was firstly agreed in Zürich in February 1959, between Great Britain, Greece, and Turkey. The Zürich Agreements were ratified a few days later in London by the representatives of the Greek and Turkish Cypriot communities, Archbishop Makarios III on behalf of the Greek Cypriots and Dr Fazıl Küçük on behalf of the Turkish Cypriots. The establishment of the new Republic was accompanied with a Treaty of Guarantee, signed between the Republic of Cyprus and Greece, Turkey, and the United Kingdom. According to this Treaty, the guarantor powers pledged to recognize and guarantee the independence, territorial integrity and security of the Republic and they undertook to prohibit any activity promoting, directly or indirectly, either union of Cyprus with any other state or partition of the island.³ This aimed at preventing the repetition of actions aiming at *enosis* or *taksim*, but at the same time, three other countries were given a role and a say over an independent and sovereign state, something

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- 1 EOKA stands for National Organisation of Cypriot fighters. It was a guerilla group led by Colonel George Grivas that fought towards overthrowing the British rule and achieving union of the island with Greece.
- 2 Joseph S. Joseph, *Cyprus: Ethnic Conflict and International Politics* (London: Macmillan Press, 1997), 39–40

that partly explains the continuing attachment of the two communities to their national centres.

Intercommunal strife, 1963- 1974

President Makarios' attempts⁴ in 1963, to amend certain provisions of the Constitution were rejected by Turkish Cypriots. This became the first of many disputed events in the early years of the Republic. While some saw Makarios' move as an attempt to prevent deadlock in decision making bodies, others perceived it as a deliberate effort to weaken the position of Turkish Cypriots in the government and to remove them from decision-making bodies. In December 1963, the killing of two Turkish Cypriots during a Greek Cypriot patrol in the walled town of Nicosia ignited violent intercommunal clashes that dragged into the first months of 1964, while after a short impasse, a new round of violence broke out in 1967. In the aftermath of these events, Turkish Cypriots retreated into a series of enclaves, a move that was counteracted with a severe economic embargo. With the intervention of the United Nations, Nicosia was divided into a Greek and Turkish sector, by an UN-patrolled demarcation line, known, since March 1964, as the "Green Line". As a result, Security Council Resolution 186 established the UNFICYP with a mandate to prevent a recurrence of fighting between the Greek and Turkish Cypriot communities.⁵ While the embargoes and restrictions to movement were lifted in 1968, Nicosia did not recover from the partition of the city. On the contrary, the participation of Nicosia was consolidated in 1974 and expanded throughout the island.

The 1974 war and the division of the island

Relations between the two communities never really improved, while the dictatorship in Greece and Turkey's expansionist aspirations resulted in a war that divided the island - a division that is still in force today. A coup d'état against President Makarios in July 1974, led by the Greek army officers and EOKA B – a paramilitary group of radical supporters of *enosis*- gave Turkey the pretext to invade the island based on the Article VI of The Treaty of Guarantee (1960) as justification to protect Turkish Cypriots who were under threat. Within a few days Cyprus was counting a heavy toll: hundreds of people died, or went missing, and thousands lost their houses and were forcibly displaced. The geographical division was soon followed by a demographic one; the green line was extended to the whole island, while a considerable Turkish military presence was established in the northern part of Cyprus. In 1975, the voluntary regrouping of populations was agreed at the Vienna intercommunal talks,

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- 3 United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Greece and Turkey and Cyprus, No.5475. *Treaty of Guarantee* signed, 16 August 1960, United Nations -Treaty Series, p.2
- 4 Known in the literature as Makarios's 13 major constitutional amendments.
- 5 The Security Council Report, Chronology of events, p11 <https://www.securitycouncilreport.org/chronology/cyprus.php?print=true>, Accessed 17.10.22

where the Turkish Cypriot population in the south moved to the north and Greek Cypriots to the south, creating two homogeneous zones divided by the UN controlled 'buffer zone.'

Since 1974, there have been many attempts to negotiate a solution to what has become known as 'the Cyprus Problem,' none of them succeeded although in certain cases like 1978, 2004 and 2017 negotiations made such progress that the solution seemed possible. The unresolved political situation is not the only factor that may have impacted the demographic composition of the urban centre of Nicosia. Other developments, some of which are outlined below, have also affected the course of development of the city and its two main communities.

The Nicosia Master Plan, 1979

Cooperation between the two communities led to rehabilitation of areas of Nicosia severely affected by the war. The Nicosia Master Plan was a daring collaborative initiative of Lellos Demetriades and Mustafa Akıncı, leaders of the Greek Cypriot and Turkish Cypriot local authorities of Nicosia respectively, with the aim to solve tangible and quotidian problems caused by unplanned development following the 1974 war and the division of the island. The project started in 1977 when the leaders of the two communities of Nicosia agreed on the need for a common sewerage system. In 1979, under the umbrella of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the leaders agreed to work, together with their technical teams, on the improvement of the existing and future habitat and human settlement conditions of the citizens of Nicosia. A bicommunal multidisciplinary team of national and international experts such as town planners, architects, civil engineers, sociologists, economists, etc. was formed in 1981 to prepare a joint Master Plan which remains in force until today.

The unilateral proclamation of 1983

After the intercommunal conflict of 1963-1964 and the retreat of Turkish Cypriots into the enclaves, the Turkish Cypriot leadership explored new forms of governance. An administrative body was formed and operated under different titles reflecting the aftermath of the conflict, the intercommunal negotiation process of 1968-1974 and the political expectations of the community. In 1983 the Turkish Cypriot leadership unilaterally declared the establishment of the 'Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus' (15 November), which was declared illegal by the UN Security Council in resolution 541. The regime is hitherto only recognised by Turkey which continues to station approximately 35,000 troops in the island. After 1974, many Turkish Cypriots are said to have left their homes and workplaces in the centre of Nicosia while Turkish

nationals with different socio-cultural backgrounds and generally lower income levels, were given economic incentives to migrate to the island and claim vacated properties of the displaced Greek Cypriot population.⁶

The granting of work permits to Third country nationals, 1990s

Due to lack of workers, the Republic of Cyprus became, in the beginning of 1990s, from a country of immigrants, a host country for thousands of third country nationals, when approval was given by the Ministry of Councils for granting work permits. Immigration to Cyprus increased in the second half of the 2000's, with the influx of European citizens, following Cyprus' accession to the European Union in 2004.

The opening of the crossings in 2003

On 23 April 2003 restrictions on movement across the Green Line were eased and people were allowed to cross the dividing line for the first time since 1974. This change prompted urban rehabilitation aided by UN and EU programmes and encouraged business activity within the old city. This was followed by the referendum on the reunification of the island based on the proposed United Nations Plan- known as the Annan Plan after the Secretary General of the UN, Kofi Annan- a year later. The majority in the Greek Cypriot community voted against, while the majority of the Turkish Cypriot community voted in favour of the plan. The opening of the first crossing point ('Ledra Palace' crossing point) was, in fact, a landmark event and, as an extension of this, the opening of a crossing point on Ledra Street followed on 3 April 2008. Currently (2023), there are nine open crossing points.

Cyprus's accession to the European Union, 2004

Despite the Cyprus problem, on May 1, 2004, Cyprus became a full EU Member State, along with the other nine acceding countries. The accession of Cyprus into the Union inevitably had a significant impact on the economic development of the island, its demographic composition due to the influx of European citizens, and the government and administration of the country which had to adapt to EU laws and regulations. This event, however, also created a further chasm across the divide, demographically, culturally, and financially, as the EU *acquis* is suspended in the northern part of the island.

The economic crisis in 2013

The events of March 2013 made Cyprus a headline on the news around the world, when the Eurogroup and the recently inaugurated President of the Republic of Cyprus, Nicos Anastasiades agreed to a rescue deal that would include

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- 6 Mete Hatay, *Beyond Numbers: An Inquiry into the Political Integration of the Turkish 'Settlers' in Northern Cyprus*, (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre, 2005).

the bail-in of uninsured and insured depositors in all Cypriot financial institutions. As experts claimed, the consequences were both direct and enduring. The haircut of deposits in the country's two largest banks was unprecedented in conception and scale and dealt a huge blow to the Cypriot economy.

The Covid-19 pandemic 2020

On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared COVID-19, the disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2, a pandemic, following a rising spread of a potentially lethal virus. The world was alarmed. Countries sealed borders, schools closed, people started wearing masks and "social distancing". A few days before an announcement by the World Health Organisation, the leaders of the two communities in Cyprus and the members of the Technical Committee on Health met to discuss how to deal with this unexpected eruption of the pandemic. Even though hitherto Cyprus had not Covid-19 cases, the Minister of Health announced the closing of four of the crossings, a measure that lasted for 15 months.

METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH PROBLEMS

The main source of data was the Censuses carried out by the Republic of Cyprus, in 1960, 1973 (micro census), 1982, 1992, 2001, 2011. Any demographic changes that occurred after 2011 are to become visible when the results of the 2021 census become available, but this falls out of the scope of this research. Preliminary results of the 2021 census that have been published online while this overview was being written are included in this overview where necessary. Much of the Census information was available online on the Cyprus Government Statistics Service website⁷ and the rest at the library of the Ministry of Finance.⁸ Regarding the areas of the island where the Republic of Cyprus does not exercise effective control (hereafter referred to as the 'Turkish Cypriot administration') data was found in the Statistical Yearbooks and Census publications (1978, 1996, 2006, and 2011) kept by the statistics department of the Turkish Cypriot administration.⁹ A good source of information was also the published PRIO Cyprus Centre (PCC) reports¹⁰, as well as the 1992 Alfons Cucó report which contained useful information for the whole of Cyprus.¹¹

The largest volume of the data we have gathered related to the whole of the island and no specific information was available for the urban centre of Nicosia. Therefore, where possible, secondary sources were used to draw a more coherent picture of the capital's centre. In this overview we make some more general observations which will complement data visualization on the interactive map of the project.

Collecting the data was not an easy process, because information taken from both sides was not always comparable. More specifically, these are the main challenges we encountered:

- 1 Separate censuses across the divide, conducted on different years: Apparently, one of the consequences of the status quo on the island is that the Censuses conducted by the Republic of Cyprus cover only the areas under its effective control, while a separate process was conducted in the areas under Turkish Cypriot administration.
- 2 Different categories in age, nationality/religion between Censuses within the same community, as well as between the two communities.
- 3 Differentiation in regions; Nicosia's regions listed in the 1960 Census are different from those listed in the subsequent censuses. Additionally, censuses conducted by the Turkish Cypriot administration include regions that were not included in the Land Registry Department of the Republic before 1974 and therefore, cannot be included in this overview, because comparisons would not be valid.

The table below provides a summary of the differences we

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- 7 Statistical Service, Republic of Cyprus: <https://www.cystat.gov.cy/el/default>
- 8 The library of the Ministry of Finance is on the first floor of the main building of the Ministry. Special thanks to Mrs Loukia Makri, Georgia Ioannou, Maria Hadjiprokopi and Thomas Gregoriou for their help and guidance during this project.
- 9 NÜFUS SAYIMI, 2011, August 2013; Statistical Yearbook 2013-2020, Statistics and Research Department of the Turkish Cypriot administration.
- 10 The PRIO Cyprus Centre (PCC) is an independent, bi-communal research centre in Cyprus and part of the Peace Research Institute Oslo (PRIO) network. Since its inception in 2005 it is committed to research and dialogue with the aim to contribute to an informed public debate on key issues relevant to an eventual settlement of the Cyprus problem: <https://cyprus.prio.org/>
- 11 Alfons Cucó, Report on the demographic structure of the Cypriot communities, 27 April 1992, Doc.6589, 1403-23/4/92-4-E. Available online: <https://assembly.coe.int/nw/xml/XRef/X2H-Xref-ViewHTML.asp?FileID=6916&lang=EN>

located between the censuses:

Table 1. Republic of Cyprus censuses

Year	Area	Ethnic/Religious Group	Gender	Nationality	Age per region
1960	Nicosia Town, Kaimakli, Omorfita Pallouriotissa, Eylenja ¹² Athalassa, Trachonas, Orta Keuy	Greeks, Maronites, Armenians, Turks, British, Gypsies, Other, for the regions	Provided	No further nationality than religion	Not per region but for urban Nicosia, (the categories are for the economically active population, for these categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • under 15 • 15-24 • 55 & over
1973 (Micro census)	Nicosia Town and Orta-Keuy, Pallouriotissa, Kaimakli, Omorphita	Not provided	Provided	Greeks and Other (only a total for Turks)	Age data are provided only for the whole of Cyprus, not separately for each region
1976	Regions provided for the city of Nicosia: -within the walls - outside the walls	Not provided	Provided	Greek Cypriots and foreigners	Not provided
1982	19 regions	Not provided	Provided	Not provided	Available only for the Nicosia municipality area as a whole
1992	19 regions	Yes, for the whole are under the control of the Republic, by gender (Data provided in the Census of 2001, Vol.1)	Data provided per region	No	Data provided per region
2001	19 regions	Yes, for the whole are under the control of the Republic, as well as by gender for urban and rural Nicosia	Data provided per region	Only the total for urban Nicosia is provided, but it lists all countries	Data provided per region
2011	19 regions	Yes, for the whole are under the control of the Republic, by gender	Data provided per region	Yes, Cypriots, EU, Third country nationals AND sex and age per country of origin	Data provided per region

Table 2. Turkish Cypriot administration censuses

Year	Regions provided	Religion	Gender	Nationality	Age per region
1960	Nicosia Town, Kaimakli, Omorfita Pallouriotissa, Eylenja, Athalassa, Trachonas, Orta Keuy	Yes (Greeks, Maronites, Armenians, Turks, British, Gypsies, Other)	Yes	No further nationality than religion	Not per region but for urban Nicosia, (the categories are for the economically active population): • under 15 • 15-24 • 55 & over
1978	no	no	no	no	for the whole of Cyprus only
1996	no	no	no	no	for the whole of Cyprus only
2001					
2006	yes	no	yes	('citizenship')TRNC, TRNC/Turkey, TRNC/Other, Turkey, Other countries (listed)	no, only for Nicosia
2011	yes	no	yes	('citizenship') TRNC,TRNC/Turkey, TRNC/Other, Turkey, Other countries (listed)	no, only for Nicosia

4 An additional impediment to the proper documentation of our data was the fact that it is prohibited by law to refer to streets, areas or neighborhoods in the areas northern of the buffer zone, with their current names.¹³ This provoked further confusion for, had we opted for refereeing to these places with their pre-1974 names, the documentation would not be fully accurate; some of the places would not be recognizable and others would necessarily be left out. On the other hand, we cannot use the current names for we will be committing an offense and be liable to conviction. We therefore had to proceed with caution and ensure that the place names mentioned are those approved and in use in the areas controlled by the Republic or use descriptive terms for places that we cannot name at all.

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- ¹² Eylenja is today's Aglantzia
¹³ According to section 6 of the amendment of the *Περί της Διαδικασίας Τυποποίησης των Γεωγραφικών Ονομάτων της Κυπριακής Δημοκρατίας Νόμος του 1988*, which was officially published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Cyprus on 19.07.2013

MAIN OBSERVATIONS:

A. Internal displacements

The data we have gathered, along with insights drawn from previous reports, suggest that the demographic characteristics of Cyprus, and by extension, of Nicosia, have been influenced by political developments. Undoubtedly, the prolonged conflict -commencing before 1960 and persisting until the 1974 war- had significantly impacted the island's demography. The events that occurred during this period – briefly explained in the first part of this overview- have probably had the most catalytic effect on Nicosia's demography. Population displacement and emigration resulting from this conflict have led to new realities and needs which were promptly manifested in the demographic makeup of the island. The ethnic segregation that ensued and the establishment of the Green Line in March 1964, played a pivotal role in altering Nicosia's demographic composition. In essence, the internal immigration and formation of the enclaves demonstrated that the division between the two communities as clearly delineated in the constitution, also acquired a crucial geographical dimension.¹⁴ The most important enclaves were formed in Nicosia, where the majority of the 12,500 internally displaced persons found themselves concentrated in the Turkish quarter of the city. Many individuals originally residing in neighbourhoods in the southern part of the city such as Strovolos, were compelled to relocate there.¹⁵ Furthermore, the mass exodus from the island of the Cypriot population for reasons related to the political uncertainty and high unemployment¹⁶, the Immigrant Settlement Project of 1966 and the 1975 relocation agreement can be identified as major factors contributing to the shifts in demographic composition within Nicosia.

Operating with a high degree of autonomy, the enclaves were able to maintain an administration akin to a 'state', encompassing a legislature, police, social services and a post office, and an army, despite economic embargoes and movement restrictions.¹⁷ In 1968, when economic sanctions were gradually relaxed, only a limited number of those who had previously fled their homes, returned permanently to their villages.¹⁸ Additional relocations were documented following the events of 1974 when the division of Nicosia had become an established reality, marked by the extension of the Green Line throughout Cyprus.

It is worth acknowledging that the geographical separation of the two communities began long before 1974. A substantial number of people had already migrated as early as the 1950s due to the unsettling situation. Records reveal that approximately 16,515 Turkish Cypriots emigrated between 1955 and 1973, with a significant surge continuing in the 1960s, the primary years of intercommunal conflict.¹⁹ A report compiled by Gürel and

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- 14 Olga Demetriou, *Displacement in Cyprus: Consequences of Civil and Military Strife- Report 1 Life Stories: Greek Cypriot community* (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre, 2012), 5; Hatice Kurtuluş & and Serma Purkis, 'Kuzey Kıbrıs'a Türk Göçünün Niteliği ve Göçmenlerin Ekonomik Sosyo-Mekânsal Bütünleşme Sorunları', Proje No: 106K330, (Ankara, 2009), 2
- 15 Nurit Kliot and Yoel Mansfeld, "Resettling Displaced People in North and South Cyprus: A Comparison", *Journal of Refugee Studies* 7, no. 4 (1994), 334; Nurit Kliot and Yoel Mansfeld, "Case studies of conflict and territorial organization in divided cities", *Progress in Planning* 52, (1999), 167-225; Gürdallı, H., & Koldaş, U. "Kıbrıs Cumhuriyeti'nden Kuzey Kıbrıs Türk Cumhuriyeti'nin İnşasına Giden Süreçte Lefkoşa'da Mekânın ve Mimarının Siyasi Dönüşümü: 1963-1983", *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 6(4), (2017)748-772.
- 16 Stavros T. Constantinou, "Economic Factors and Political Upheavals as Determinants of International Migration: The case of Cyprus", *Πρακτικά του πρώτου Διεθνούς Συμποσίου Κυπριακής Μετανάστευσης: Ιστορική και Κοινωνιολογική Θεώρηση*, Κέντρο Επιστημονικών Ερευνών 29-31 Αυγούστου 1986 (Nicosia: Cyprus Research Centre, 1990), 145. "It is important to note that 16,515 Turkish Cypriots emigrated between 1955 and 1973, but particularly in the 1960s—the major years of intercommunal conflict." Ioannides 1991:20-28 quoted in Kliot, Mansfeld, 1994, 335.
- 17 Rebecca Bryant, *Displacement in Cyprus: Consequences of Civil and Military Strife, Report 2- Life Stories: Turkish Cypriot community* (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus Centre, 2012), 9
- 18 Ibid.
- 19 Ioannides 1991, 20-28 quoted in Kliot and Mansfeld, "Resettling Displaced People", 335

Özersay, indicates that by 1974, approximately 142,000 Greek Cypriots from the northern part of the island had relocated to areas in the southern part (30% of the total Greek Cypriot population at the time) and an additional 45,000 who were already displaced from the southern region of the island, migrated northward (raising the overall figure to 60,000 or 40 percent of the total Turkish Cypriot population).²⁰ These figures highlight that by the time of the Vienna Agreement²¹ was ratified in 1975, approximately 30% of the entire island's population had already experienced displacement from their homes in the southern and the northern parts of the island.²² The population exchange established by the Vienna marked the conclusive stage in segregating the island into two ethnically homogeneous zones culminating in the displacement of around 150,000 Greek Cypriots and 115,000 Turkish Cypriots across the divide in total.²³ Notably, these figures do not include the number of people who went missing during this period, which amounted to approximately 2,000 Cypriots, with three-quarters of them being Greek Cypriots.

B. Migrations

A valuable starting point for the study of the fluctuations of the population is the 1992 Report by Council of Europe Rapporteur, Alfons Cucó, who used all the available sources to document the situation up to 1992 and make suggestions as to the efficient control of immigration in the island. Based on this report, and figures derived from the Censuses across the divide and PRIO Cyprus Centre reports, the population of the island evolved as seen on the table below:

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- 20** Ayla Gürel and Kudret Özeray, *The Politics of Property in Cyprus: Conflicting Appeals to 'Bizonality' and 'Human Rights' by the Two Cypriot Communities*, PRIO Cyprus Centre Report 3/2006 (Nicosia/Oslo:PRIO, 2006), 3.
- 21** The **Third Vienna Agreement** was a bilateral agreement reached between Turkey and Cyprus over the Cyprus dispute on 2 August 1975 where certain principles were agreed related to relocation of Greek and Turkish Cypriots within the island. [https://www.prio.gov.cy/en/agreements-the-third-vienna-agreement-\(2-august-1975\).html](https://www.prio.gov.cy/en/agreements-the-third-vienna-agreement-(2-august-1975).html)
- 22** Purkis and Kurtuluş, "Spatially Segregated", 2
- 23** Bryant and Hatay, *Sovereignty Suspended*, 75

Table 3: Cyprus Population (indicative years)

Year	Total	Greek Cypriot community	Turkish Cypriot community ²⁴
1956	528,618	417,080	91,980
1960	573,566	442,138	104,320/104,942
1973	631,778		
1974 ²⁵	641,000	506,000	118,000 ²⁶
1976		497,600	130,100
1982		522,845	153,200
1992		615,013	
1996			188,662
2001		703,529	
2004		727,500	
2005		706,000	215,000
2006			256,644
2011		840,407	286,257
2019		880,600	382.230 (projected)
2020			382,836 (projected)
2021		923,272	

Sources: Cucó Report; Republic of Cyprus Statistical Service, (Population 1974-2019); Statistical yearbook 2020 of the Turkish Cypriot administration; Mete Hatay, *Population and politics in north Cyprus: an overview of the ethno-demography of north Cyprus in the light of the 2011 Census*, Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus, 2017. (In bold: RoC Census years; In light purple: Turkish Cypriot administration Census Years; in dark purple: Census conducted across the divide)

Cucó asserts that the more substantial increase in the Turkish Cypriot population in 1960 likely resulted from a higher number of Greek Cypriots emigrating during this period. After 1974, obtaining actual figures became impossible as Censuses had been replaced by estimates. Figures in Table 3 also reveal fluctuations in the *de jure* population in the areas controlled by the Republic of Cyprus that can be explained by some of the key events this project deals with. More precisely, from 1973 until 1976, the population decreased by 133,899 as a result of the 1974 war. However, during this period, the Turkish Cypriot community experienced significant population growth which according to Cucó it could not be justified by the natural increase of the population and must have been due to substantial influx of migrants.²⁷

Indeed, researchers and analyzers of the demography of the northern part of the island have also supported this perspective. Between 1975 and 2003, 45,689 'citizenships' were granted by the Turkish Cypriot administration to Turkish nationals - the most were granted between 1976 and 1981, and then between 1993 and 1997 - 4650 to second or third generation Cypriots, 1094 to Bulgarian Turks and 1825 to people from Third countries.²⁸ More specifically, Purkis and Kurtuluş identified the first of the three migration waves from Turkey to have started after the events of 1974 and extended until the 1980s. This wave was fueled by incentives related to agricultural land and houses.²⁹ In February, 1975, under the "Regulation on Closing the Workforce Deficit in the Turkish Region of Cyprus with the Labor Force to be Sent from Turkey", a special agreement³⁰ was signed between Turkey and the Turkish Cypriot administration to get approximately 30 thousand migrants from Turkey.³¹ Mete Hatay suggests that the 'settler' label be restricted to the subcategory of 'agricultural labour', whose migration to the island formed part of a deliberate settlement policy pursued by both Turkey and the Turkish-Cypriot authorities following the partition of the island in 1974.³² The facilitated migration phase concluded by the late 1970's, while international pressure and internal opposition led to the amendment of the law that revoked property privileges for the immigrants who arrived after 1982.³³

The 2006 census conducted by the Turkish Cypriot administration showed that the *de jure* population of the Turkish Cypriot community grew from 188,662 in 1996, to 256,644 in 2006, meaning a 36% increase within a ten-year period. Of the total of 256,644, 70,525 (27,5%) were Turkish Republic citizens and 8,088 (3,5%) citizens of Third Countries. Also, 130,392 of the total figure for 2006 are those with one or both their parents born in Cyprus, while the total figure of people born in Cyprus is 147,405.³⁴ Notably, the 2006 census reveals that 11,925 citizens

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- 24** This column refers to the whole of the population living northern of the buffer zone.
- 25** The figure of Greek Cypriots includes the Maronite, Armenian and Latin Christian minorities who had opted for membership of this community.
- 26** According to the Cucó report, the Turkish-Cypriot Administration provided a different number for Turkish Cypriots for that year, 115,758.
- 27** Cucó report, 1992, 6-7
- 28** Hatay, *Beyond Numbers*, p.13 and Appendix I: Citizenships Granted, 1974-2003
- 29** Purkis and Kurtuluş, "Spatially Segregated", 1-22
- 30** The agreement brought workers (namely skilled in the fields of Livestock, Horticulture, Agriculture, Fishing and other) under the status of 'Tarım İşgücü Statülü Personel' [Agricultural Labor Status Personnel]. According to a study, the workers would earn the right to a retirement compensation fee after 10 to 15 years of labour and return to their homelands. The same study states that though some returned, many remained and were granted identity cards with the right to vote, as well as land (though without deeds). (Ahmet Gürkan Atay, 2010: 70).
- 31** Purkis, Kurtuluş, 2013: 5. Gürdallı, Koldaş, 2017: 762 It is proposed that the 'settler' label be restricted to the subcategory of 'agricultural labour', whose migration to the island formed part of a deliberate settlement policy pursued by both Turkey and the Turkish-Cypriot authorities following the partition of the island in 1974 in Mete, Hatay, *Beyond Numbers: An Inquiry into the Political Integration of the Turkish 'Settlers' in Northern Cyprus*. Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus centre, 2005, vii)
- 32** Hatay, *Beyond numbers*, vii
- 33** Mete Hatay, *Is the Turkish Cypriot population shrinking? An overview of the Ethno-demography of Cyprus in the Light of the Preliminary Results of the 2006 Turkish-Cypriot census*, (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus centre, 2007)
- 34** Hatay, *Is the Turkish Population shrinking*, 30

of Turkish origin declared that they had arrived in Cyprus before 1979.³⁵ The following years the number of 'citizenships' granted ranged between 400 to 1200, with some exceptions: 40 in 1986 (the lowest) and 2,287 in 1990 (the highest).³⁶ Towards the end of the 1990s, the last migration wave from Turkey transpired; the second occurred in the late 1970s/early 1980s driven by opportunities within Cyprus, rather than Turkey, for radical agricultural policies in Turkey led to unemployment issues, prompting thousands to leave the country and settle in the walled city of Nicosia.³⁷ The unilateral proclamation of the regime northern of the buffer zone might have worked as an encouragement to Turkish citizens who wanted to relocate, as it gave the impression of a virtual stability and maintenance of the status quo. Hatay and Bryant explain that this wave was driven by a series of neo-liberal privatizations that occurred in the northern part of the island, making it attractive for owners of small enterprises as well as highly skilled professionals such as financial experts hired by local or offshore banks, lecturers who teach in the universities, and businessmen who had investments on the island.³⁸

Foreign nationals in the Republic of Cyprus

Since 1990, the population of the Republic of Cyprus has been gradually increasing due to we may say, a variety of reasons: new labour legislation, accession of the country to the European Union; immigration flows due to conflict and instability in neighboring countries, as well as the Cyprus investment programme of 2016, through which the Cypriot citizenship was granted to high income earners and investors in exchange for the purchase of property in Cyprus worth at least €500,000.³⁹ Specifically, in 1990 shortage of manpower in some branches of the economy such as the building trade, public works and the service industries led the trade unions and employers to sign an agreement whereby migrant workers may be called in.⁴⁰ According to a Council of Ministers' decision of March 15, 1990 "Permit of entry and temporary employment" could be given to 1500 foreigners for a start to work on certain sectors such as hotels, construction and clothing to cover for the deficit of 1700 work positions that was predicted for 1990.⁴¹ This decision marked a significant change in the labour market and the demographic character of the island. Indeed, population data show that, while from 1979 until 1989 there was a rather steady increase in the population ranging between 1.2-1.8%, the percentage surged to 2.7% in 1994.⁴² As of 2012, the increase percentage fell to under 1% and became negative for the following two years, probably due to the economic crisis that started in 2008 and culminated with the 2013 bail-in. Between 2007 and 2011 8,3647 foreign citizens/nationals arrived to the island, while in the period 2012-2015,

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- 35** Hatay, *Is the Turkish Population shrinking*, 47
- 36** Mete Hatay, *Beyond Numbers: An Inquiry into the Political Integration of the Turkish 'Settlers' in Northern Cyprus* (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus centre, 2005), appendix 1. Data becomes available from 1976.
- 37** Purkis, Kurtulus, 'Spatially Segregated', 7
- 38** Mete Hatay & Rebecca Bryant, *Migrant Cities Research: Nicosia north* (Nicosia: British Council, 2008), 8
- 39** According to the decisions of the Council of Ministers (of 13.09.2016 and the subsequent decision of 21.05.2018), non-Cypriot investors can acquire Cypriot citizenship by naturalization as well as a Cypriot passport for them and their families (with exception based on the Population Register Law of 2002 - 2017).
- 40** Cucó, *Report*, 17
- 41** Απόφαση Υπουργικού Συμβουλίου 15.03.1990, υπογεγραμμένη από τον Γραμματέα του Υπουργικού Συμβουλίου στις 23.3.90 κατόπιν πρότασης Αρ 175/90 με τίτλο «Παραχώρηση Άδειας για Προσωρινή Απασχόληση σε Αλλοδαπούς Εργαζόμενους», που κατατέθηκε από τους Υπουργούς Οικονομικών, Εσωτερικών και Εργασίας και Κοινωνικών Ασφαλίσεων.
- 42** CY STAT Table B1. Πληθυσμός de jure κατά φύλο, 1974-2019 and B2. Δημογραφικά Μεγέθη

29,533 people left the island. The population of the island has returned to growth figures as of 2016 onwards.⁴³ In a nutshell, in 1990, 6,718 were registered in Cyprus while, by 2011 this numbered reach 119,867, as shown in Table 5.⁴⁴

Table 4 & 5: Immigration of EU/Third country nationals to Cyprus, 1980-2011:

	Before 1980	1980-1984	1985-1989	1990-1994	1995-1999	2000-2004	2005-2009	2010-2011
Nationality								
EU citizens	928	895	1353	3739	7987	17494	42865	19373
Third country citizens	103	118	198	782	2865	9938	30084	13656

Source: Μεταναστευτική Κίνηση, 1981-2018
 COPYRIGHT © :2014, REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS, STATISTICAL SERVICE

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⁴³ CY STAT Table B1. Πληθυσμός de jure κατά φύλο, 1974-2019 and B2. Δημογραφικά Μεγέθη

⁴⁴ Labour Statistics, 1990-2011, Statistical Service, Republic of Cyprus

Indeed, based on the 2001 census, the period from 1992 to 2001 witnessed a notable increase in the percentage of residents holding foreign citizenship, surging from 4.2% to 9.4%. Notably, female foreign nationals constituted 55.7% of the total population of foreign nationals, while males comprised the remaining 44.3%. Furthermore, when considering age demographics, the segment of the population aged 20-39 accounted for 45.1% of foreign nationals in Cyprus, in contrast to 27.3% among Cypriot citizens. In terms of geographic distribution, the Nicosia district emerged with the highest count of foreigners, encompassing 35.1% of the total, with 31.4% located in urban Nicosia and the remainder residing in rural areas. Interestingly, when adjusted for each town's population, Paphos exhibited the greatest proportion of resident foreign nationals, while Nicosia ranked third in this regard.⁴⁵

In 2001, among the EU citizens, the largest share is held by people born in Greece (25,285), Romania (22,868), United Kingdom (22,304), and Bulgaria (17,923) while from the Third Countries category, the majority were born in Philippines (9,338), Russia (7,515), Sri Lanka (7,196), Vietnam (7,005), India (2,868), Syria (2,685) and Ukraine (2,610). Another interesting information that surfaces from the Statistical Service Immigration data is that while in all the countries mentioned, the ratio of men and women is around 50:50 in all countries of origin, we notice that this changes when it comes to people coming from Philippines, Sri Lanka and Vietnam where women make 96%, 84%, and 96% respectively, as they usually come for housekeeping and caretaking positions.⁴⁶

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⁴⁵ , *Census of Population 2001*, vol.1
Statistical Service, Republic of Cyprus, 31

⁴⁶ *ibid*

Table 6: Foreign workers in the Republic of Cyprus, 1990-2011.

Source: Labour Statistics 1990-2011, Statistical Service, Republic of Cyprus

The demographic composition of the urban centre of Nicosia also reflects these fluctuations. Although data showing the exact number of non-Cypriots residing in the centre of Nicosia are not available until 2001, data extracted from the 2001 and 2011 census show an increase in the population of foreign nationals of the area in alignment with an increase in the whole population of the Nicosia Municipality area increased from 48,221 in 1982 to 56,848 in 2021.⁴⁷ According to the 2001 census which provides figures for the totality of the urban area of Nicosia⁴⁸ -not just the Nicosia municipality area- 20,345 of the 200,686 residents, -around 10% of the total population of urban Nicosia- were of non-Cypriot origin. 9,379 of these were nationals of EU countries;⁴⁹ 2,928 of other European countries, 6,819 of Asian countries, 536 of the United States, 543 of African countries and 57 of countries in the Australian continent. Ten years later, according to the 2011 Census, the population of urban Nicosia increased to 239,277 residents of which 47,671 were foreign nationals; 26,799 of which were citizens of EU countries and 20,872 of Third Countries. In the regions within the jurisdiction of Nicosia Municipality out of 55,014 residents, 9,812 were EU citizens and 8,331 were citizens of Third countries.⁵⁰

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- ⁴⁷ Preliminary Census 2021 results published on the website of the Statistical Service, cystat.gov.cy
- ⁴⁸ Urban Nicosia includes these areas: Municipalities of Nicosia, Agios Dometios, Engomi, Strovolos, Aglantzia, Lakatamia, Latsia, Yeri and the Anthoupoli communities.
- ⁴⁹ 9253 were from EU countries and 126 from countries that would become full members with the 2004 EU enlargement.
- ⁵⁰ 2011 census – in the Census there is always a 'Not stated' column which applies to almost all categories, like age, gender, religion, or citizenship.

According to the 2011 census the more residential areas of the urban centre of Nicosia are Agios Andreas, Kaimakli, Agios Antonios, Pallouriotissa, and Agioi Omologites, while the areas attracting the fewer residents are those closer to the buffer zone, i.e. Nebethane, Tabakhane, Faneromeni, Omeriye, Agios Ioannis, Agios Kassianos, Arab Ahmet, Yeni Cami, and Omorfita. The most populated areas attract residents from all the three categories mentioned in the table below. However, ratios differ depending on the area. In Kaimakli and Panagia (Pallouriotissa), Cypriots make up 78.3% and 72.9% of the population respectively, while in Agios Andreas, the percentage falls to 68% and in Agioi Omologites to 58.6%. In the core of the urban centre though the ratio changes, i.e. in the area of Trypiotis which includes the most commercial streets of Makariou, Evagorou, Stasinou, etc. Cypriots make up 42.3% of the population, while in the areas of Faneromeni and Agios Savvas this percentage falls to 25%. A helpful observation that derives from the demographic composition of the urban centre is that the population of urban Nicosia -not only the area within the walls- is mainly youthful. Within the jurisdiction of the Nicosia Municipality, the average age stands at 39 years. Notably, the proportion of individuals aged 25-64 comprises 59.8% of the entire population, a slight elevation compared to the corresponding figure of 57.16% for the broader Nicosia district. According to the census of the Statistical Service in 2011, the total percentage number of permanent residents of Cyprus who are foreign nationals amounts to 21.4%, i.e. 179,547 persons. In Nicosia the percentage was 18.9%, the lowest compared to other cities, with the highest being in Paphos, reaching 34.9%. The concise historical overview of migratory patterns in Cyprus, particularly when juxtaposed with the prior census conducted in 2001, reveals a significant transformation in the socio-cultural and demographic landscape. Notably, the 2001 census indicated a mere 9.4% of the total population as non-Cypriots, further underscoring the substantial shifts that have transpired.⁵¹ The 2001 census revealed that the majority of foreigners in Cyprus belong to the productive 15-64 years old age group, women are more than men, and in general, foreigner's educational level is higher than Cypriots, debunking probably a wrong perception held by the society.

C. The 2011 censuses

During the year 2011, Censuses were conducted on both sides of the divide. It was the first census of the population living under Turkish Cypriot administration which was undertaken under the unofficial United Nations oversight and the primary purpose of this endeavour was to furnish pertinent data for the reunification negotiations in process.⁵² The census excluded military areas but included ports and hotels. Although there were claims that there

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- ⁵¹ MUNET, *European municipalities Network, Cyprus and Migration: Integration Principles and the role of local government* (Nicosia: 2013) 23
- ⁵² Mete Hatay, *Population and politics in north Cyprus: an overview of the ethnography of north Cyprus in the light of the 2011 Census*, (Nicosia: PRIO Cyprus), 2017, vii

was some under-counting during the census⁵³, it is probably the one that bears the most validity. The 2011 census was carried out by the Turkish Cypriot administration according to the UN's Principles and Recommendations for Population and Housing Censuses. Given this, we could attempt to compare it with the Republic of Cyprus 2011 census regarding the demographic composition of the centre of Nicosia across the divide and this our main observations:

- The 2011 census of the Republic of Cyprus revealed a population of 840,407 – 21,9% more than the previous census of 2001- of which 667,398 were Cypriots, 106,270 EU citizens and 64,113 Third Country citizens. The 2011 census of the Turkish Cypriot administration revealed a *de jure* population of 286,257⁵⁴ excluding Turkish military and their families residing in the military bases; 190,494 were 'TRNC' 'citizens', 80,550 were Turkish nationals and 15,215 had other nationalities.
- The population in the part of Nicosia north of the buffer zone is predominantly young; 69,932 fall into the age groups of 0-44 while less than half, 24,892 fall into the age groups of 45-85+ (see the table below).⁵⁵ The same applies to urban Nicosia in the Republic of Cyprus where 149,100 residents fall into the age groups 0-44, and 90,177 in the age groups 45-80+. The percentage of the younger group to the whole population is 73.1% for the Turkish Cypriot community and 62.3% for the Greek Cypriot community, an indication that the Greek Cypriot population is slightly older than the Turkish Cypriot population of Nicosia. In general, the Republic of Cyprus 2011 census revealed a small increase in the older population of the island, with the percentage of people under the age of 65 to be 13,3% comparing to 11,7% of 2001 while the percentage of the age group 0-14 fell to 16,1% from 21,4%.
- While the RoC 2011 census refers to the local population as Cypriots and distinguishes it from the other categories, namely, EU citizens and Third Country citizens, the authorities in the Turkish Cypriot administration make a more elaborate distinction as to the local population, namely, TRNC only, TRNC-Turkey, and TRNC-other. The census provides a list of countries of origin, of which most residents are coming from Turkey (30,449), Turkmenistan (1013), and Pakistan (465) of the total population of 94,824 (82,929 people reside in the Nicosia central subdistrict). In the Republic of Cyprus, the population of urban Nicosia amounts to 239, 277 residents of which 26,779 are EU citizens and 20,872 Third Country citizens.

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- 53** Hatay, *Population and politics*, 27
Undercounting was attributed to a social media campaign calling for a boycott of the census, failure to reach some dwellings near or on the Green Line or in remote locations, while probably some numerous unregistered workers hid away those days.
- 54** De jure population refers to the permanent residents, while the de facto population means all persons presented on the island the day of the census.
- 55** Census of the Republic of Cyprus 2011; DPO Census of the Turkish Cypriot administration, 2011, 44

Table 7: Population in the part of the island under Turkish Cypriot administration, by age and gender

Source: Statistical Department of the Turkish Cypriot administration

Table 8: Population in the areas under the effective control of the RoC

Source: 2011 Census of the Republic of Cyprus, Statistical Service, RoC

- Based on the two 2011 censuses, the area of Nicosia under the jurisdiction of the Nicosia Municipality and Turkish Cypriot Municipality of Nicosia are formed as follows – the neighborhoods listed are the ones in existence before 1960:

Table 9: Current population in Nicosia regions across the divide

Region	Male	Female
Agios Andreas	5767	2950
Trypiotis	2158	1175
Nebethane	189	103
Tabakhane	299	182
Faneromeni	512	255
Agios Savvas	581	262
Omeriye	206	101
Agios Antonios	5,801	3006
Agios Ioannis	221	111
Tahtekale	826	411
Chrysaliniotissa	124	66
Agios Kassianos	82	35
Kaimakli	11564	5948
Panagia	12398	6361
Agios Konstantinos & Eleni	3209	1666
Agioi Omologites	10,528	5587
Arap Ahmet	50	29
Yeni Cami	215	99
Omorfita	284	147
Abdi Çavuş	315	253
Akkavuk	458	335
Haydarpaşa	80	75
İbrahimpaşa	327	239
İplikpazarı	163	66
Agios Kassianos (north of the buffer zone)	145	88
Karamanzade	168	183
Mahmutpaşa	172	142
Agia Sofia	510	368
Yenişehir/Neapoli	1864	1851

Population in the regions of the centre of Nicosia, 2011

Censuses of Population 2011

17512

- | | | |
|------------------|------------------------------|--|
| ● Agios Andreas | ● Chrysaliniotissa | ● AKKAVUK |
| ● Trypiotis | ● Agios Kassianos | ● HAYDARPAŞA |
| ● Nebethane | ● Kaimakli | ● İBRAHİMPAŞA |
| ● Tabakhane | ● Panagia | ● İPLİKPAZARI |
| ● Faneromeni | ● Agios Konstantinos & Eleni | ● Agios Kassianos
(northern of the buffer zone) |
| ● Agios Savvas | ● Agioi Omologites | ● KARAMANZADE |
| ● Omeriye | ● Arap Ahmet | ● MAHMUTPAŞA |
| ● Agios Antonios | ● Yeni Cami | ● AGIA SOFIA |
| ● Agios Ioannis | ● Omorfita | ● YENİŞEHİR/Neapoli |
| ● Tahtekale | ● ABDİ ÇAVUŞ | ● Ayios Loukas |

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Through this brief overview we have tried to communicate some observations based on the available data on Nicosia's demography. As underlined above, we have encountered several challenges which have rendered comparisons, both between the two communities, as well as between different time periods, complicated. Numerical information based on the Censuses will appear in full detail on the project's interactive map. This overview works mostly as an introduction to the map and an analysis of the project's methodology and aims.

An insight into the data confirmed the major effect the turbulent decades of 1960s and 1970s had on the demographic makeup of Nicosia. Forced internal displacements, emigration of Cypriots and facilitated migrations to Cyprus were the immediate effects of the conflict on the demography of the city that continued until the 1980s, especially in the Turkish Cypriot community, with the influx of people from Turkey. Within the Greek-Cypriot community, the demographic composition was mainly affected by the 1990 Labour legislation, as well as by the country's accession to the European Union; both developments facilitated the influx of foreign citizens into the country, and this is reflected in the centre of the capital as well. Nicosia's population was not significantly affected by the 2013 crisis, as implied by the data. The effect of the crisis was more economic, and this is examined in the Business Activity review. It seems, however, that the population of the urban centre has remained stable over the years, and less old than expected, as more young people choose the walled city and the surrounding areas to settle down. However, there is a considerable non-Cypriot population within the urban centre whose needs should be considered in the decision-making processes.

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Notes:

- 1 **Disclaimer:** CYENS Centre of Excellence is a research and innovation centre that operates under the motto “Inspired by Humans Designed for Humans”. Its vision is to produce world-class research that drives innovation towards a social and economic benefit, while conducting excellent, internationally competitive scientific research in the areas of visual sciences, human factors and design, communication, and artificial intelligence. It is supported by the European Commission, the Republic of Cyprus and its founding partners: the Municipality of Nicosia, the Max Planck Institute for Informatics (MPI), University College London, the University of Cyprus, the Cyprus University of Technology, and the Open University of Cyprus. DeepNic is a research project, hosted by CYENS and funded by the Research Promotion Foundation. In conjunction with key socio-political events that occurred between 1960 and 2020, it investigates the evolution and transformation of Nicosia’s urban centre in three thematic areas: demography, business activity and monument building. DeepNic’s research team includes both Greek Cypriots and Turkish Cypriots and primary research was conducted across the Green Line. The project acknowledges the suffering that the people of the island have experienced during the island’s recent history and that terminology related to the conflicts between the Greek and Turkish Cypriot communities can be politically charged. CYENS aims to be objective and to use scientific inquiry as a tool that transcends political and social differences. Taking all this into consideration, CYENS’ decision for any publications derived from the DeepNic project is to use language that is as inclusive and respectful towards as many sensibilities as possible, with multiperspectivity and critical thinking as guiding principles, and to present DeepNic’s research results objectively, without any intention to offend or alienate. With this project, CYENS does not, in any way, afford any entities recognition that has not been granted by law.
- 2 The term “TRNC” is only mentioned in the text when data are copied out from the Censuses conducted by the statistical service of the Turkish Cypriot administration. This is done for accuracy purposes only and does not imply recognition of the illegal regime.
- 3 The words *citizen* and *citizenship* are put in inverted commas when it is used for the population north of the buffer zone for the regime is not internationally recognized .
- 4 **Thanks:** The production of this overview would not have been possible without Thomas Nikidiotis, who helped with the documentation of numerical data from the RoC Statistics Department and Iliana Koulafeti and Loizos Kapsalis for their valuable feedback and cross checking.

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